

Coleoptera species	X2KA53234	X2KA53235	X2KA53240	X2KA53242	X2Z80702	X2Z80703	X2Z80704	X2Z80710	X2Z80711	X2Z80713	X2Z80714	X2Z80715	X2Z80734	X2Z80734R	X2Z80736	X2Z80737	X2Z80738	X2Z80739	X2Z80740
Brachonyx pineti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hylastes brunneus	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atheta bosnica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus pilula	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis figurata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis livida	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis tristis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rhagonycha fuscitibia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amara bifrons	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calathus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calodromius spilotus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	52	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus pumilio	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anastrangalia sanguinolenta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0
Monochamus sartor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	58	0
Oxymirus cursor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Stictoleptura rubra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Donacia clavipes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doydirhynchus austriacus	0	0	0	0	218	0	0	4480	0	3694	0	221	43347	0	0	0	0	131	0
Anatis ocellata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calvia quatuordecimguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Myzia oblongoguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anthonomus phyllocola	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	16	0	0	1141	16261	0	0	6	5	0
Brachyderes incanus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	234	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cleopomiarus graminis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hypera nigrirostris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis linearis	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2023	0	0
Magdalis memnonia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus pauxillus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus singularis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	353	0	0	0	28	0	0	220	0	4212

Coleoptera species	X2KA53234	X2KA53235	X2KA53240	X2KA53242	X2Z80702	X2Z80703	X2Z80704	X2Z80710	X2Z80711	X2Z80713	X2Z80714	X2Z80715	X2Z80734	X2Z80734R	X2Z80736	X2Z80737	X2Z80738	X2Z80739	X2Z80740
Stenus brunnipes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Stenus impressus	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Isomira semiflava	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	0	0

Coleoptera species	XZZ80742	XZZ80743	XZZ80744	XZZ80745	XZZ80746	XZZ80747	XZZ80748	XZZ80749	XZZ80751	XZZ80753	XZZ80754	XZZ80755	XZZ80756	XZZ80757	XZZ80758	XZZ80759	XZZ80762	XZZ80763	XZZ80764	XZZ80766	XZZ80769
Brachonyx pineti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hylastes brunneus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atheta bosnica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus pilula	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis figurata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis livida	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis tristis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rhagonycha fuscitibia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amara bifrons	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calathus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calodromius spilotus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus pumilio	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anastrangalia sanguinolenta	0	0	0	0	0	17	59	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Monochamus sartor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Oxymirus cursor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Stictoleptura rubra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Donacia clavipes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doydirhynchus austriacus	0	0	0	0	54	0	0	0	0	0	62	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anatis ocellata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calvia quatuordecimguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Myzia oblongoguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anthonomus phyllocola	0	0	0	0	126	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	118
Brachyderes incanus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cleopomiarus graminis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hypera nigrirostris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis linearis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	500
Magdalis memnonia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus pauxillus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus singularis	0	71	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35	89064	0	98	0	26	0	0	0

Coleoptera species	XZZ80770	XZZ80771	XZZ80772	XZZ80773	XZZ80774	XZZ80775	XZZ80776	XZZ80777	XZZ80778	XZZ80779	XZZ80783	XZZ80784	XZZ80785	XZZ80786	XZZ80787	XZZ80788	XZZ80789	XZZ80791	XZZ80792	XZZ80794
Brachonyx pineti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hylastes brunneus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atheta bosnica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus pilula	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis figurata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis livida	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis tristis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rhagonycha fuscitibia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amara bifrons	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calathus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calodromius spilotus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus pumilio	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anastrangalia sanguinolenta	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Monochamus sartor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Oxymirus cursor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Stictoleptura rubra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	519	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Donacia clavipes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doydirhynchus austriacus	0	89	0	357	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anatis ocellata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calvia quatuordecimguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Myzia oblongoguttata	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	280	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anthonomus phyllocola	0	0	0	0	0	139	126080	81371	38	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Brachyderes incanus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cleopomiarus graminis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hypera nigrirostris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis linearis	0	0	0	55	0	0	0	0	0	9539	0	0	0	0	0	0	66	0	0	0
Magdalis memnonia	0	0	0	0	125	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus pauxillus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus singularis	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	113	0	0	233	0

Coleoptera species	XZZ80795	XZZ80805	XZZ80807	XZZ80812	XZZ80813	XZZ80814	XZZ80815	XZZ80816	XZZ80818	XZZ80819	XZZ80820	XZZ80821	XZZ80822	XZZ80823	X3Y03503	X3Y03504	X3Y03505	X3Y03506	X3Y03507	X3Y03508	X3Y03510
Brachonyx pineti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hylastes brunneus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atheta bosnica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus pilula	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis figurata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis livida	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis tristis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rhagonycha fuscitibia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amara bifrons	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calathus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calodromius spilotus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	64	0	0
Pterostichus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus pumilio	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0
Anastrangalia sanguinolenta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Monochamus sartor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Oxymirus cursor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Stictoleptura rubra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Donacia clavipes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doydirhynchus austriacus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5572	0	0	0	0
Anatis ocellata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calvia quatuordecimguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Myzia oblongoguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anthonomus phyllocola	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	17	0	0	125	3822	0	0	0	0	0
Brachyderes incanus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1187	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cleopomiarus graminis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hypera nigrirostris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis linearis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis memnonia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus pauxillus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus singularis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	52	0	0

Coleoptera species	X3Y03511	X3Y03519	X3Y03546	X3Y03547	X3Y03548	X3Y03549	X3Y03550	X3Y03551	X3Y03552	X3Y03553	X3Y03555	X3Y03556	X3Y03557	X3Y03558	X3Y03559	X3Y03560	X3Y03562
Brachonyx pineti	0	0	0	0	304	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hylastes brunneus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atheta bosnica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus pilula	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis figurata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis livida	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis tristis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rhagonycha fuscitibia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amara bifrons	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calathus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calodromius spilotus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus pumilio	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anastrangalia sanguinolenta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Monochamus sartor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Oxymirus cursor	0	88	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Stictoleptura rubra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Donacia clavipes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doydirhynchus austriacus	0	16015	18821	6841	125	0	0	0	0	0	0	3996	0	0	0	0	0
Anatis ocellata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calvia quatuordecimguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Myzia oblongoguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anthonomus phyllocola	0	0	0	0	46	0	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	21563	359	218	0
Brachyderes incanus	0	3196	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cleopomiarus graminis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hypera nigrirostris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis linearis	0	0	0	0	54300	0	0	0	0	122	0	20	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis memnonia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus pauxillus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus singularis	0	0	4602	0	1230	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	141	0	0	1131	0

Coleoptera species	X3Y03563	X3Y03564	X3Y03565	X3Y03566	X3Y03567	X3Y03568	X3Y03569	X3Y03570	X3Y03571	X3Y03572	X3Y03573	X3Y03574	X3Y03575	X3Y03601
Brachonyx pineti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hylastes brunneus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atheta bosnica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Byrrhus pilula	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis figurata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis livida	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cantharis tristis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rhagonycha fuscitibia	0	0	0	0	0	4609	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amara bifrons	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calathus speciesy	0	0	0	0	220	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calodromius spilotus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus speciesy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pterostichus pumilio	0	0	1041	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anastrangalia sanguinolenta	0	0	0	0	18439	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Monochamus sartor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Oxymirus cursor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Stictoleptura rubra	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Donacia clavipes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doydirhynchus austriacus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anatis ocellata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Calvia quatuordecimguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Myzia oblongoguttata	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anthonomus phyllocola	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3954	0	0	0	0	0
Brachyderes incanus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cleopomiarus graminis	0	0	0	0	0	43	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hypera nigrirostris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis linearis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Magdalis memnonia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus pauxillus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Otiorhynchus singularis	0	0	0	37118	0	0	0	93	0	0	0	0	0	0

